

Optimization and Scaling of Multiple Sequence Alignment Software ClustalW on Intel Xeon Phi

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Abstract: This work is aimed to investigate and to improve the performance of multiple sequence alignment software ClustalW on the test platform EURORA at CINECA, for the case study of the influenza virus sequences. The objective is code optimization, porting, scaling and performance evaluation of parallel multiple sequence alignment software ClustalW for Intel Xeon Phi (the MIC architecture). For this purpose a parallel multithreaded optimization including OpenMP has been implemented and verified. The experimental results show that the hybrid parallel implementation utilizing MPI and OpenMP provides considerably better performance than the original code.

Keywords: Bioinformatics, ClustalW, Computer Cluster EURORA, Hybrid Programming, High Performance Computing, Multiple Sequence Alignment, Parallel Programming, Performance.

1. Introduction

In silico biological sequence processing is a key technology for molecular biology. Scientists are now dependent on databases and access to the biological information. This scientific area requires powerful computing resources for exploring large sets of biological data.

The parallel implementation of methods and algorithms for analysis of biological data using high-performance computing is essential to accelerate the research and reduce the financial cost. Multiple sequence alignment (MSA) is an important method for biological sequences analysis and involves more than two biological sequences, generally of the protein, DNA, or RNA type [1]. This method is computationally difficult and is classified as a NP-hard problem [2]. ClustalW software has become the most popular algorithm and implements a progressive method for multiple sequence alignment [3]. ClustalW computes the best match for the selected sequences, and lines them up so that the identities, similarities and differences can be seen. The basic algorithm behind ClustalW proceeds in three stages: pairwise alignment (PA), guide tree (GT) and multiple alignment (MA). Pairwise alignment computes the optimal alignment cost for each pairs of sequences. A distance matrix is built up; its entries show the degree of divergence for each pair of sequences in evolution. Distance is calculated as the percentage of nonidentity residues between two sequences. An evolutionary guide tree is constructed of the distance matrix using the sequence similarity matrix and Neighbor-Joining algorithm [4]. The tree holds values for each sequence that represent its similarity to all other sequences. The algorithm aligns the sequences progressively according to the branching order in the guide tree by first aligning the most similar pair of sequences, then the next most similar pair and so on. ClustalW phases are relatively independent. Each of the phases produces intermediate data which is used as an input for the next one. The execution time is strongly dependent on the number of sequences as well as their size. ClustalW-MPI [5] is a distributed and parallel implementation for distributed computer clusters and for traditional parallel computers.

This activity with the project PRACE-1IP is aimed to investigate and improve the performance of multiple sequence alignment software ClustalW on the computer system EURORA (Intel Xeon Phi) [6] at CINECA, for the case study of the influenza virus sequences. The objective is porting, optimization, scaling, performance evaluation and profiling of parallel multiple sequence alignment software ClustalW. For this purpose a hybrid parallel (MPI+OpenMP) version has been implemented and verified as part of the work done in order to assess the efficiency of the algorithm.

2. Experimental Framework

The experimental framework of the investigations is based on the computer system Eurora (Intel Xeon Phi) at CINECA. EURORA is a cluster made of 65 nodes of different types [6]:

Compute Nodes: There are 64 16-core compute cards (nodes). Half of the nodes contain 2 Intel(R) Xeon(R) SandyBridge eight-core E5-2658 processors, with a clock rate of about 2 GHz, while the other half of the cards contain 2 Intel(R) Xeon(R) SandyBridge eight-core E5-2687W processors, with a clock of about 3 GHz. 58 compute nodes have 16GB of memory, but the safely allocatable memory on the node is 14 GB (see PBS resources: memory allocation). The remaining 6 nodes (with processors at 3 GHz clock rate) have 32 GB RAM. The EURORA cores are capable of 8 floating point operations per cycle. 32 compute cards have two nVIDIAK20 (Kepler) GPU cards and 32 compute cards have two Intel Xeon Phi accelerators.

Login nodes: The Login node has 2 Intel(R) Xeon(R) esa-core Westmere E5645 processors at 2.4 GHz Intel Xeon (Esa-Core Westmere) E5645 2.4 GHz.

All the nodes are interconnected through a custom Infiniband network, allowing for a low latency/high bandwidth interconnection.

Intel Xeon Phi is the first Intel Many Integrated Core (Intel MIC) architecture product. Each card consists of 60 physical cores (@1.1 Ghz) and each core is able to handle up to 4 thread using hyperthreading. Each core has one Vector Processing Unit able to deliver for each clock cycle: 8 Fused Multiply and Add (FMA) floating point operations in double precision and 16 Fused Multiply and Add (FMA) floating point operations in single precision. The Phi has a peak performance of 1056 GFlops in double precision and 2112 Gflops in single precision. Each Phi coprocessor has a RAM memory of 8 GB, and a peak bandwidth of 352 GB/s.

3. Parallel ClustalW MPI Implementation for Intel Xeon Phi

Some experiments have been carried out utilizing parallel program implementation of ClustalW MPI. Influenza virus A/H1N1 sequences obtained from Genbank [7] have been used as experimental data. The objective of the experiments is to measure the parallel performance parameters of the specified parallel software. Similarity searching between RNA segments of various influenza viruses A has been carried out based on the parallel program implementation of ClustalW using MPI on EURORA system (Intel Xeon Phi) in native mode.

Detailed information about the duration of the three computational phases of the ClustalW-mpi for the case study of the influenza virus A/H1N1 are presented in Table I. The input file consists of 98 influenza virus protein sequences, each with length of 481 symbols.

Numbers of threads	Execution time, sec			
	PA	GT	MA	Total
1	1809,6	0,33	3204,55	5014,48
20	96,3	0,25	48,2	144,75
40	49,3	0,24	47,6	97,14
60	31,64	0,25	46,76	78,65
120	28,6	0,24	42,8	71,64
240	28,2	0,24	43,6	72,04

Table I. Phases duration time of ClustalW-mpi on Intel Xeon Phi architecture using various numbers of threads.

The speed-up is evaluated as a ratio of the execution time on 1 core to the execution time on 20, 40, 60, 120, and 240 threads respectively. The experimental results for the speed-up of the ClustalW algorithm on Intel Xeon Phi architecture using various numbers of threads with respect to 1 thread are shown on Figure 1.

Figure 1. Speed-up during the execution of ClustalW-mpi on Intel Xeon Phi architecture using various numbers of threads.

The experimental results and analyses of ClustalW-mpi software show that the times for parallel execution during the first stage (pairwise alignment) and the third stage (multiple alignment) decrease with increasing the number of threads, while the execution time of the second stage (guide tree construction) remains approximately constant.

4. Hybrid Parallel ClustalW Implementation for Intel Xeon Phi

The computational aspect of this project is to investigate the parallel performance in respect to the efficiency, scaling and profiling of parallel multiple alignment on EURORA system utilizing parallel OpenMP deployment and optimization of the MPI-based parallel implementation of ClustalW algorithm for Intel Xeon Phi architecture. The parallel hybrid MPI/OpenMP computational model of ClustalW algorithm for multiple sequence alignment is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Hybrid OpenMP/MPI parallel computational model of ClustalW.

The ClustalW code implementation on Intel Xeon Phi requires hybrid granularity of parallelization. Coarse granule computing for each node (multithreaded process) that runs multithreading (fine granule) of the cores within the computing node on Intel Xeon Phi [8] [9].

In order to choose an appropriate part of the code to be parallelized, we used **gprof** for profiling the program: how often each function is called and how long it takes to perform.

For this purpose, first the flag **-pg** in the Makefile is added at the end of the compilation and linking rows. Then the following command is used:

```
gprof clustalw-mpi gmon.out > gprof.output
```

The file **gprof.output** shows the profiling results in Figure 3:

Each sample counts as 0.01 seconds.

%	cumulative	self	self	self	total	
time	seconds	seconds	calls	Ks/call	Ks/call	name
25.22	1280.69	1280.69	1910035	0.00	0.00	diff
21.72	2384.01	1103.31	3908	0.00	0.00	calc_mean
16.36	3214.72	830.72	1910035	0.00	0.00	forward_pass
15.24	3988.78	774.05	1910035	0.00	0.00	reverse_pass
13.95	4697.12	708.35	4204763923	0.00	0.00	calc_score
2.84	4841.31	144.18	1	0.14	0.14	calc_similarities
2.71	4979.07	137.77	1	0.14	0.14	nj_tree
1.04	5032.09	53.02	1910035	0.00	0.00	tracepath
0.21	5042.86	10.77	57027490	0.00	0.00	prfscore
0.12	5049.20	6.34	1954	0.00	0.00	calc_prf1
0.10	5054.17	4.97	1	0.00	1.11	read_tree
0.08	5058.19	4.01	1910035	0.00	0.00	count_gaps
0.07	5061.56	3.37	3908	0.00	0.00	calc_h_penalties
0.07	5064.92	3.37	1	0.00	0.01	aln_score
0.07	5068.27	3.35	3908	0.00	0.00	calc_p_penalties
0.05	5071.01	2.74	1954	0.00	0.00	prfalign
0.04	5073.03	2.02	1	0.00	3.65	pairalign
0.04	5074.84	1.80	1954	0.00	0.00	ndiff

Figure 3. Profiling results of ClustalW-mpi.

The analysis of the ClustalW code shows that one of the time-consuming functions is `calc_similarities()`. This function is executed only once, but the execution takes a relatively large time - 144.18 sec.

The function `calc_similarities()` in the file `calctree.c` is parallelized utilizing OpenMP. In each **For Loop** a parallel for OpenMP directive is placed. This results in having each OpenMP thread assigned to a different sequence every time until the work is completed.

Initial benchmark tests have shown that increasing the number of threads for the same number of MPI processes and nodes decreases the execution time significantly (Figure 4). The function execution takes only 0.05 sec.

0.08	4899.39	3.69	3908	0.00	0.00	calc_h_penalties
0.07	4902.70	3.31	1	0.00	0.01	aln_score
0.06	4905.77	3.07	3908	0.00	0.00	calc_p_penalties
0.06	4908.71	2.94	1954	0.00	0.00	prfalign
0.04	4910.68	1.97	1	0.00	3.63	pairalign
0.04	4912.60	1.92	1954	0.00	0.00	pdiff
0.02	4913.44	0.84	89909402	0.00	0.00	open_penalty2
0.02	4914.19	0.74	60308256	0.00	0.00	open_penalty1
0.01	4914.80	0.61	58666896	0.00	0.00	ext_penalty1
0.01	4915.37	0.57	57869664	0.00	0.00	ext_penalty2
0.01	4915.81	0.44	1954	0.00	0.00	add_ggaps
0.01	4916.08	0.27	3908	0.00	0.00	calc_gap_coeff
0.00	4916.26	0.18	1	0.00	0.00	clustal_out
0.00	4916.36	0.10	1954	0.00	0.00	calc_prf2
0.00	4916.46	0.10				del
0.00	4916.54	0.08	1913953	0.00	0.00	info
0.00	4916.60	0.06	1866	0.00	0.00	mark_group2
0.00	4916.65	0.05	3	0.00	0.00	two way split
0.00	4916.70	0.05	1	0.00	0.00	calc_similarities
0.00	4916.75	0.05	1	0.00	1.15	malign
0.00	4916.79	0.04	472868	0.00	0.00	local_penalty

Figure 4. Profiling results of ClustalW-mpi-openmp.

5. Parallel Performance Evaluation Utilizing a Hybrid (MPI+OpenMP) Parallel ClustalW implementation

The objective of the experiments is to measure the parallel performance parameters of the hybrid ClustalW MPI+OpenMP parallel program implementation on EURORA system (Intel Xeon Phi) in native mode. Some experiments have been carried out utilizing hybrid parallel program implementation of ClustalW. Influenza virus A/H1N1 sequences have been used as experimental data.

Detailed information about the duration of the three computational phases of the ClustalW-mpi-openmp for the case study of the influenza virus A/H1N1 is presented in Table II. The input file consists of 98 influenza virus protein sequences, each with length of 481 symbols.

The speed-up is computed as a ratio of the execution time on 1 core to the execution time on 20, 40, 60, 120, and 240 threads respectively. The experimental results for the speed-up using various numbers of threads with respect to 1 thread for the case of ClustalW-mpi-openmp are shown on Figure 5.

Numbers of threads	Execution time, sec			
	PA	GT	MA	Total
1	1809,6	0,33	3204,55	5014,48
20	58,41	0,24	31	89,65
40	28,45	0,22	30,28	58,95
60	19,01	0,22	30,27	49,5
120	16,64	0,22	30,8	47,66
240	15,6	0,23	31,6	47,43

Table II. Phases duration time of ClustalW-mpi-openmp on Intel Xeon Phi architecture using various numbers of threads.

Figure 5. Speed-up during the execution of ClustalW-mpi-openmp on Intel Xeon Phi architecture using various numbers of threads.

The experimental results and analyses of ClustalW software show that the time for parallel execution during the first stage (pairwise alignment) decreases with increasing the number of threads. The experimental results presented in Table III. show that the MPI+OpenMP program implementation achieves higher reduction in execution time as the first stage and the third stage. The total execution time is decreased by approximately 1.5 times.

Numbers of threads	PA	MA	Total
20	1,65	1,55	1,61
40	1,73	1,57	1,65
60	1,66	1,54	1,59
120	1,72	1,39	1,50
240	1,81	1,38	1,52

Table III. ClustalW-mpi-openmp execution time vs. ClustalW-mpi on Intel Xeon Phi architecture using various numbers of threads.

6. ClustalW 2.1 Code Porting and Optimization on Intel MIC Accelerators

During the project the latest version of ClustalW code (version 2.1) has also has been partly optimized for Intel MIC accelerators. In the current implementation the first part (pairwise alignment) of the program was parallelized for improving the performance on Intel MIC accelerators.

The experimental results are presented in the Table IV. Achieved speed-up for the whole code is shown on the Table IV. and achieved speed-up for the parallel section of ClustaW 2.1 code is shown on the Figure 7.

Numbers of threads	Execution time for Clustalw-2.1, sec			
	PA	GT	MA	Total
1	2837,4	1304,2	973,5	5115,1
20	740,5	1304,2	973,5	3018,2
40	527,8	1304,2	973,5	2805,5
60	471,3	1304,2	973,5	2749,0
120	442,1	1304,2	973,5	2719,8
240	440,8	1304,2	973,5	2718,5

Table IV. Experimental results for the parallel part the parallel section of the code.

Figure 6. Speed-up during the execution of optimized version of ClustalW 2.1 on Intel Xeon Phi using various numbers of threads.

Figure 7. Achieved speed-up for the parallel part (pairwise alignment) of clustaw 2.1 code.

The experimental results for the parallel section of the code shows that the speed-up increases as well as reaching the core numbers limitation.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

The parallel software for multiple sequence alignment ClustalW has been optimized through multithreaded implementation. The ClustalW code is ported and is available on the Intel MIC architecture (EURORA system). It is best suited to work in native Xeon Phi MPI mode in a combination of MPI tasks and threads.

Parallel performance evaluation of multiple sequence alignment software ClustalW utilizing MPI and OpenMP on Intel Xeon Phi architecture has been investigated experimentally. Parallel performance parameters such

execution time and speed-up have been measured. The performance estimation and analyses show that the hybrid parallel program implementation utilizing MPI and OpenMP of ClustalW software for multiple sequence alignment scales well as the number of the cores increases up to 60 cores. On the other hand the performance of the MPI+OpenMI implementation is better than MPI only implementation, since the total execution time is decreased by approximately 1.5 times.

The optimized code is universal and can be apply for other similar research projects and experiments in the field of bioinformatics and will allow researchers to conduct their experiments on even more powerful supercomputers. They will be able to perform simulations with very large amounts of data.

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